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Child Upbringing Parental Styles and Personal Values of Adolescents in Pentecostal Churches in Ede South Local Government Area, Osun State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Adolescence is a challenging time that entails self-discovery and social connection with others. Parental styles are patterns of behaviors, attitudes, and approaches that a parent uses when interacting with and raising their child. Personal values are a set of guiding principles and beliefs that help differentiate between “good” and “bad.” These are concepts like integrity versus dishonesty or hard work versus cutting corners. Personal values influence people’s behaviors, relationships, and everyday life. This study child upbringing, parental styles, and the personal values of adolescents attending selected Pentecostal churches in Ede South Local Government Area, Osun State, Nigeria. It aims to identify prevalent parental styles in child upbringing, understand the personal values exhibited by adolescents, examine the influence of child upbringing parental styles on personal values developed by Adolescents, and assess the impact of the religious environment in Pentecostal churches on the personal values of Adolescents. The study employs a descriptive survey design method, using a questionnaire to collect data from a sample of 200 adolescents. Findings reveal that parents in these religious communities significantly exhibit the four types of parental styles. The religious environment plays a substantial role in shaping personal values, both positively and negatively, impacting adolescents' moral development, resilience, and social responsibility. Parents and guardians are encouraged to actively engage with their adolescents in navigating religious diversity. The recommendation aims to create a more informed, inclusive, and tolerant environment for adolescents within Pentecostal churches in Ede South Local Government Area.

Keywords: Child Upbringing, Parental Styles, Adolescents, Personal Values, Ede South Local Government, Pentecostal Churches.

Introduction

In contemporary times, the phase of adolescence has gained recognition as a distinctive phase of life that comes with unique requisites. It is recognized as a phase, rather than a singular moment, in an individual's life. Along with physical and mental changes, societal perceptions and expectations also undergo a shift during this period. As a part of the process of crafting an identity, they may experiment with diverse roles, behaviours, and philosophies. This recognition of adolescence as a unique phase of life, coupled with the researchers' experiences on various behavioural pattern among adolescents while reaching out to secondary school students in Ede and its environments, has prompted researchers and scholars to delve deeper into understanding its intricacies, particularly concerning the influence of child upbringing parental styles on the development of personal values among adolescents in Ede.

Exploring the dynamics between parental guidance and adolescent autonomy sheds light on how adolescents navigate the complexities of identity formation and value acquisition within the context of their familial and social environments. This exploration becomes especially pertinent within the framework of religious communities, such as Pentecostal churches, where familial values often intersect with spiritual teachings and community norms.

Understanding the interplay between parental styles and personal values among adolescents attending Pentecostal churches in Ede, Osun State, Nigeria, holds implications for individual development and individual development, community cohesion, and cultural preservation. By examining the influence child upbringing parental styles have on Adolescent personal values, researchers aim to uncover patterns that may contribute to a more nuanced understanding of adolescent development within religious contexts. Additionally, assessing the influence of the ,spiritual environment in Pentecostal churches on personal values provides insights into the role of faith-based institutions in shaping moral frameworks and ethical decision-making processes among youths. The study of child upbringing parental styles is based on the idea that parents differ in their on on parenting patterns, and that these patterns can significantly impact their children's personal value development and well-being. Scholars said that parenting styles are distinct from specific parenting practices since they represent broader patterns of practices and attitudes that create an emotional climate for the child (Hong,2021). Parenting styles also encompass how parents respond to and make demands on their children.

To effectively explore the influence of child upbringing Parental style on the personal values of Adolescents, it must be well understood that there are several types of parental styles in child upbringing such as Authoritarian, Authoritative, Permissive, and Uninvolved parental styles as classified by a psychologist (Vijay, Christy; Gonsalves, Kavita Peter, Ramesh, and Naveen, 2022) and various values adolescents can develop. Hence, the researcher focuses on the four types of parental styles mentioned above and personal values such as cultural,, ethical and spiritual values.

Statement of the Problem

Adolescence is a critical developmental period when individuals form their identities and personal values. Parental styles are the totality of approaches and behaviour of parents in raising their adolescents (Bak-Coleman, 2021). This method has a significant influence on adolescents' value systems and behaviours. Furthermore, religious institutions, such as Pentecostal churches, play an important role in shaping the moral and ethical beliefs of their adolescents. (Mamarasulovich, 2022)

The influence of parental styles on the personal values of adolescents in Pentecostal churches in the Ede South Local Government (L. G.), Area is not well understood. This is because there is limited research on this topic, and the existing research is often limited in scope. Additionally, the cultural context of Nigeria is complex, and it is important to consider this context when studying the influence of parental styles on the personal values of adolescents (Bak-Coleman, 2021). While studies on parental styles and adolescent development exist (Bak-Coleman, 2021). There is limited research specifically examining the influence of child upbringing parental styles on the personal values of adolescents attending Pentecostal churches in Ede South L.G. Area, Osun State, Nigeria. This is the gap the researchers worked on. The unique cultural and religious context of Ede, with a strong presence of Pentecostal churches, also calls for an investigation into how parental styles in these religious communities influence the formation of personal values in adolescents.

Literature Review

Concept of Personal Values

Fundamentally, the concept of personal values mirrors internalized beliefs concerning what is deemed right, significant, or fulfilling in life. Individuals frequently construct a hierarchy of values, with certain principles considered fundamental and non-negotiable. These values not only shape behaviour but also play a pivotal role in aligning life goals and aspirations, providing a framework for decision-making. (Shelton and Elliot, 2018)

Personal values are the principles and beliefs that guide our decision-making and behaviour. They help us to differentiate between what is good and bad, and they shape how we move through the world. According to a Scholar, we can learn personal values from the people around us (the first example is our parents), or we can develop them on our own through personal growth (Tascherrau-Dumouchel, Mathias, Stefan, 2022). Adolescents often adopt most of their values from their family members (parents especially), but they start to build their own value systems as they age. Your personal values are the principles that you hold most dear. They are the foundation of your ethical compass and guide your thoughts, words, and actions. When we live by our values, we feel a sense of purpose and fulfillment (Lilach and Shalom, 2022). Scholar K.M Sheldon & A. J Elliot. made it known that "Our personal values can change over time, but our core values tend to remain relatively stable." (K.M Sheldon & A. J Elliot, 2018) It is very important to take time to identify our personal values, as this can help us to clarify our goals and priorities and also help us make better decisions in life. The notion of personal values constitutes a deep

and intricate facet of human identity, encompassing the firmly rooted principles and beliefs that steer an individual's decision-making and conduct. These values are inherently subjective, influenced by factors such as cultural nuances, upbringing, education, and personal experiences. Serving as a moral guide, personal values establish the bedrock of one's identity, molding priorities and contributing to a sense of purpose (Lilach and Shalom, 2022).

Cultural and societal influences exert substantial impacts on the formulation and expression of personal values. Yet, individuals may also foster values that challenge established norms, emphasizing the intricate interplay between personal values and the broader social context. Negotiating situations where values clash necessitates careful consideration, as individuals may be compelled to make decisions involving trade-offs between competing values (Bak-Coleman, 2021).

Effective communication of personal values is pivotal in forging meaningful relationships, given that shared values often contribute to stronger connections. Simultaneously, comprehending and respecting divergent values is vital for navigating potential conflicts. Regular introspection and self-awareness are integral to elucidating and conveying personal values, ensuring harmony with an individual's evolving sense of self. Personal value is a broad goal, varying in importance and underlying and guiding attitudes and behaviour. 'Personal value is divided into two major components: the content of values and the commitment to those values' as stated by Tascherrau-Dumouchel, Mathias, and Stefan (2022). The content of values is the things people value, such as power, achievement, hedonism, stimulation, self-direction, universalism, benevolence, tradition, conformity, and security. Living under one's core principles provides a sense of contentment, authenticity, and purpose. An individual who prioritizes and behave by their values report higher levels of pleasure and inner peace. Personal values impact relationships and interactions with others because they shape one's views toward empathy, collaboration, justice, and understanding (Xiong, Hao, Mengmeng, Chengfu, Xin, Congshu & Yifan). Personal values must be defined via introspection and contemplation. It entails recognizing and defining the values and ideals that are truly important to a person. This self-awareness enables people to make deliberate choices and decisions that are consistent with their beliefs, resulting in a more rewarding and purpose-driven existence. It must be noted that everyone has values, but each individual has a unique set of values. These distinctions, as said by an author, are influenced by a person's culture, personal upbringing, life experiences, and a variety of other factors. The simplest method to define personal values is to consider the individual's personality and habits. Values eventually intertwine into people's personalities and become a part of them (Weber, 2017).

Religious Values

Religious values are typically derived from the values expressed in religious texts or from the influence of the lives of religious figures. Religious values can vary from religion to religion, but some common values are shared by many religions. Such values include love, compassion, forgiveness, justice, and mercy (Lilach and Shalom, 2022). These values can play an important role in people's lives, providing guidance and inspiration, and helping people to make better

choices. The beliefs of an individual are often centered around religion, so religion can be the origin of that individual's values. When religion is defined heuristically, it can be used by individuals, communities, or societies to answer their existential questions with the beliefs that their religion teaches. According to a scholar, Religions offer answers to life's ultimate questions, which can influence our values and the answers that religions provide to these questions can have a profound impact on our values. For example, if a religion teaches that the meaning of life is to love and serve others, then we may develop values of compassion and kindness. Or, if a religion teaches that suffering is a test of our faith, then we may develop values of perseverance and resilience (Lilach and Shalom, 2022).

Ultimately, the values that we hold dear are a reflection of our individual beliefs and experiences. However, the answers that religions provide to existential questions can play an important role in shaping our values. This research was conducted in a way that is consistent with Christian beliefs.

Cultural Values

The values of a particular culture can have a significant impact on how adolescence is experienced. For example, adolescents may be given more freedom and autonomy in cultures that value independence and self-reliance than in cultures that value obedience and conformity (Priti, Shilpa, Shagufta, and Sapana, 2023).

Economic Factors

Economic factors can also play a role in shaping the experience of adolescence. In cultures where there are limited economic opportunities, adolescents may be expected to start working and contributing to the family income at a younger age (Priti, Shilpa, Shagufta, and Sapana, 2023). This can limit their opportunities for education and self-exploration.

Social Norms

Social norms can also influence the experience of adolescence. In cultures where there are strong expectations about how adolescents should behave, they may feel pressured to conform to these expectations, even if they do not agree with them (Chloe, Sommerfield, Britta, 2020). This can make it difficult for adolescents to develop their own identities and make their own choices.

The different experiences of adolescents across cultures can have a significant impact on the lives of adolescents. In cultures where adolescence is a time of great freedom and exploration, adolescents may have more opportunities to develop their own identities and make their own choices. In cultures where adolescence is a time of greater restriction and control, adolescents may feel more constrained and may have fewer opportunities to express themselves (Priti, Shilpa, Shagufta, Sapana, 2023).

It is important to be aware of the different experiences of adolescents across cultures in order to understand the challenges and opportunities that adolescents face. By understanding the cultural

context in which adolescents are growing up, we can better support them as they navigate this important stage of development.

Parents and other adults who care for and work with adolescents need to stay up-to-date on adolescent development and the realities of adolescent life. Adolescents face a variety of complex and ever-changing challenges, including social media and mental health disorders. By understanding these challenges, adults can provide more effective support and encouragement to young people (Pearce, Uecker, Melinda, 2019).

Adolescent Development

Adolescence is a transitional phase of growth and development between childhood and adulthood. The World Health Organization (WHO) defines an adolescent as any person between the ages of 10 and 19. This age range falls within WHO's definition of young people, which refers to individuals between the ages of 10 and 24.

However, the definition of adolescence varies across cultures. In some societies, adolescence is narrowly equated with puberty and the physical changes that lead to reproductive maturity (Yeo-eun, Yu, Wolters and Eric, 2023). In other societies, adolescence is understood in broader terms that encompass psychological, social, and moral development, as well as physical maturation. In these societies, adolescence typically refers to the period between the ages of 12 and 20 and is roughly equivalent to the word teens.

Bard, a large language model from Google AI, has pointed out that adolescence is a universal stage of development, but the way it is experienced and understood varies greatly across cultures. In some cultures, adolescence is a time of great freedom and exploration. Adolescents are encouraged to experiment with different identities and roles, and they are given a great deal of autonomy. In other cultures, adolescence is a time of greater restriction and control. Adolescents are expected to conform to traditional norms and expectations, and they may have limited opportunities for self-expression (Luitse, Wiebke, and Eric, 2023).

The duration of adolescence also varies across cultures. In some cultures, adolescence is a relatively short period, lasting from the onset of puberty to the early twenties. In other cultures, adolescence can last much longer, extending into the mid-twenties or even thirties (Luitse, Wiebke, and Eric, 2023).

The different experiences of adolescence across cultures can be attributed to several factors, including:

Influence of Parental Styles on Adolescent Personal Values

Parental styles are categorized under three major forms: authoritarian, authoritative or democratic, permissive or laissez-faire, and self-indulgence or un-involving. The authoritarian parental style consists of parents who are often strict, and harsh. Authoritative parents are flexible and responsive to their children's needs but still enforce reasonable standards of conduct (Oyebode, 2020). At the same time, permissive or laissez-faire parents are those who impose few restrictions, rules, or limits on their children. Reports have shown that authoritarian parental styles have a negative connotation in literature because of the negative behaviour outcomes of

adolescents and children. However, on the same, note outcome of some research revealed that authoritarian parents yield positive effects on adolescents. Some found that authoritative parental style has more positive effects on adolescents' behavior (Lilach and Shalom, 2022). Permissive or laissez-faire parents without well-defined or clear-cut goals and such parents play a passive role in the rearing of children.

Authoritarian parents enforce their beliefs and opinions as laws of the mind (nature). They believe that what they know is the reality and facts can be imposed from outside. There is no need for the child to work on his way. Raising a child like this is simple, easy, and fast like raising hormone-injected tomatoes. No questioning, inquiring just accepting without proof. Even though the facts that are presented by the authority are valid and real because children have to accept them, the children would not own them (Chloe, Sommerfield, Britta, 2020). Children would not own them because there is no self-effort involved in the process. They have to prove these facts to their minds to make them their own. Authoritarian parents set strict rules and standards and expect their children to obey them. Everything is thought and predetermined by parents, the only thing that children have to do is follow the instructions.

The children of authoritarian parents actualize the wills and orders of their parents; therefore, they often either cannot or will not take responsibility for their own actions (Lilach and Shalom, 2022). If children do not feel responsible for their actions, they may find themselves engaging in a variety of actions that could cause harm both to themselves and to others. Such a situation provides the appropriate conditions for delinquent behaviour. It has been found that children of authoritarian parents have higher rates of delinquency than children of non-authoritative parents (Priti, Shilpa, Shagufta, Sapana, 2023).

Children of authoritarian parents have difficulty in differentiating between right and wrong because in their case right and wrong depends on the authority. Therefore, morality is conditional, with conditions determined by external forces. Again, because children are not raised as independent individuals, they cannot express a need for and/or develop independently a set of humanistic moral values. Dependent people cannot develop moral values. Authoritarian parents seek to ensure that their children obey rules and standards; their relationship with their children is basically based on a power conflict. As adolescent grows, older authoritarian disciplinary styles decline.

The connection between parental approaches and individual values stands as a crucial element in human development, molding the convictions and actions of individuals over their lifetimes. Parenting styles, encompassing the emotional atmosphere and behavioral methods employed by parents, wield a considerable influence over the internalization of personal values in their children. Through the processes of modeling and observation, parents assume primary roles as exemplars, with children often absorbing the values demonstrated by their caregivers, thus shaping their own set of personal values (Yeo, Yu, Wolter, and Eric, 2023). Authoritative parenting, characterized by a harmonious blend of warmth and clear expectations, correlates with positive outcomes, and nurturing values like responsibility and empathy. In contrast, authoritarian parenting may foster the internalization of values stressing conformity and

obedience, while permissive parenting may contribute to values associated with autonomy and self-expression. Inconsistencies in parenting styles may generate confusion for children, affecting the establishment of a cohesive set of personal values. Communication styles, cultural and religious influences, and negative experiences further contribute to the intricate relationship between parental styles and personal values. While parental approaches exert significant influence over values, individuals also retain the capacity for independent thought, enabling the development of values that may diverge from those imparted by their parents (Luitse, Wiebke, 2021). The interplay among these factors highlights the nuanced and dynamic nature of the association between parental styles and personal values.

Role of Personal Values in Adolescent Development

The role of personal values in adolescent development is significant and multifaceted. Personal values encompass an individual's core beliefs, principles, and ethical standards, which guide their thoughts, behaviour, and decision-making processes (Priti, Shilpa, Shagufta, Sapana, 2023). During adolescence, a period marked by self-discovery and identity formation, personal values play a crucial role in shaping a young person's sense of self and their place in the world. Adolescents often begin to question and explore their values as they navigate through various life experiences and interactions. These values can stem from cultural, familial, religious, and societal influences, as well as personal reflections (Chloe, Sommerfield, Britta, 2020). As adolescents strive to establish their identities, their personal values serve as a foundation for understanding their priorities, aspirations, and the kind of person they want to become.

Moreover, personal values influence the choices adolescents make, impacting their relationships, academic pursuits, and involvement in their communities. For instance, an adolescent who values honesty and integrity may prioritize academic integrity and transparent communication in their interactions. On the other hand, an adolescent with a strong value for social justice might become actively engaged in advocacy and community service. It's important to note that personal values are not static; they can evolve and change over time as adolescents gain new experiences and insights (Sheldon and Elliot, 2018). These values also play a role in moral development, as adolescents grapple with complex ethical dilemmas and gradually refine their sense of right and wrong.

Personal values are integral to adolescent development as they contribute to the formation of identity, guide decision-making, and shape the path to adulthood. Understanding the interplay between personal values and development can provide valuable insights into the motivations and behaviour of adolescents (Chloe, Sommerfield, Britta, 2020).

Personal values are a broad goal, varying in importance and underlying and guiding attitudes and behaviour. Personal values are formed in adolescence, which may affect long-term cognitions and behaviour. A previous study reported that universalistic values, which were classified as self-transcendence, were related to the creation of meaningfulness.

Religious Influence on Adolescent Values

Religious influence on adolescent values is a substantial and intricate aspect of their development. Adolescents often look to their religious beliefs and practices as a source of guidance and

meaning, which can profoundly shape their values, attitudes, and behaviour (Yue, Shihong, Wenjuan, Yanfeng, Pingping & Y. Qingqiang, 2019).

Religious teachings provide a framework for understanding moral and ethical principles. Adolescents who are actively engaged in a religious community often absorb values that align with their faith's teachings (Juuso, 2021). For example, religions may emphasize compassion, kindness, honesty, and respect for others. These values can become integral to an adolescent's sense of right and wrong, influencing their interactions with peers, family, and society.

Religious rituals, such as prayer, meditation, or attending worship services, can foster a sense of connection to a higher purpose and a broader community. This connection can instill values related to humility, gratitude, and a sense of responsibility to contribute positively to society. At the same time, adolescents may also engage in a process of questioning and reinterpreting religious teachings as they develop their understanding of the world. This critical examination can lead to a more nuanced and personalized set of values. Some adolescents might align closely with their religious teachings, while others may integrate aspects of multiple belief systems or develop values that are more secular in nature (Francois & Rossetti, 2020).

Religious influence on adolescent values can extend to various domains of life, including decisions about friendships, relationships, career choices, and social justice advocacy. For instance, an adolescent influenced by their religion's emphasis on service to others might be drawn to volunteer work or community service projects (Juuso, 2021). It's important to recognize that the impact of religious influence on values varies from person to person and depends on factors such as the strength of religious upbringing, exposure to diverse perspectives, and personal introspection. Open communication between adolescents, their families, and their religious communities can provide a space for exploring and discussing how religious values intersect with their developing sense of self and values. Religious influence on adolescent values is a complex interplay between faith, personal reflection, and societal norms. It can play a significant role in shaping adolescents' moral compass, guiding their decisions, and contributing to their overall sense of purpose and identity (Bak-Coleman, 2021).

Adolescents' religious and spiritual development is influenced by many factors, including their parents, peers, institutions, and culture. These social influences can provide examples and feedback that shape how adolescence thinks about, practice, and experience religion and spirituality (Lilach and Shalom, 2022).

Religious influence on adolescent values plays a significant role in shaping the moral and ethical compass of young individuals. Pentecostal Churches, a subset of Christian denominations, are known for their strong emphasis on the Holy Spirit, spiritual gifts, and charismatic expressions of faith (Bak-Coleman, 2021). In these churches, the Holy Spirit is central to the believer's experience, with practices such as speaking in tongues and the manifestation of spiritual gifts being integral to their worship services. Pentecostal worship is characterized by its lively and expressive nature, often involving energetic music, clapping, dancing, and the use of spiritual gifts. Charismatic leadership within these churches guides congregants and is seen as essential for facilitating a deeper connection with God.

In addition to their charismatic worship, Pentecostal Churches (such as RCCG, DLBC, MFM, and Winners Chapel) are part of the broader evangelical movement, emphasizing evangelism and the spreading of the Gospel message. These churches vary in beliefs and practices, and they are often actively engaged in community outreach and social programs (Juuso, 2021). The eschatological beliefs within Pentecostalism, such as the expectation of the Second Coming of Christ and the rapture, are also important aspects of their theological framework. With millions of adherents worldwide, Pentecostalism has become a global movement, contributing to the diversity of religious influences on the values and beliefs of adolescents within their congregations. The impact of Pentecostalism on adolescents is profound, as it introduces them to a dynamic religious environment that fosters strong spiritual experiences, emphasizes the role of the Holy Spirit, and encourages active participation in charismatic worship and evangelical efforts. This influence can have a lasting impact on the values and worldviews of young individuals, shaping their understanding of faith and morality during the critical stage of adolescence (Bak-Coleman, Mark, Wolfram, Carl, Miquel, 2021).

Adolescent Development in Pentecostal Contexts

Adolescent development within Pentecostal contexts is a subject that reveals the interplay between religious beliefs and the psychosocial growth of young individuals. Pentecostalism, characterized by its emphasis on spiritual experiences, gifts of the Holy Spirit, and vibrant worship practices, contributes to a unique environment that shapes adolescents' cognitive, emotional, and social development (Lilach and Shalom, 2022).

Pentecostal beliefs often emphasize the transformative power of personal conversion experiences and the Holy Spirit's role in guiding one's life. These theological foundations can influence how adolescents perceive their identity, purpose, and moral compass. Adolescents within Pentecostal communities may experience a heightened sense of community and belonging, as well as opportunities for leadership and service within the church (Xiong, Hao, Mengmeng, Chengfu, Xin, Congshu & Yifan, 2021). These experiences can contribute to their self-esteem and identity formation.

At the same time, the distinct practices of Pentecostal worship and spiritual engagement might also introduce challenges related to the balance between religious commitments and the secular demands of adolescence. Negotiating these tensions can impact adolescents' psychological well-being and the development of their autonomy (Weber, 2017). The spiritual guidance and mentorship often available within Pentecostal contexts can play a significant role in shaping adolescents' values, relationships, and aspirations.

Adolescence development in Pentecostal contexts is a multifaceted process influenced by the unique religious dynamics and beliefs of Pentecostal Churches. Within these contexts, adolescents experience a distinct blend of spiritual and social influences that impact their growth and values. Pentecostalism, known for its emphasis on the Holy Spirit and spiritual gifts, shapes the religious landscape in which adolescents navigate their journey from childhood to adulthood (Syamsul, Utama, Sekar, Prayitno & Waston, 2023).

In Pentecostal contexts, the evangelical mission is paramount, with a focus on spreading the message of the Gospel. Adolescents are actively involved in evangelism and community outreaches, which not only strengthens their faith but also nurtures a sense of purpose and responsibility towards others. This engagement provides opportunities for adolescents to apply their values in practical ways, contributing to their moral and ethical development (Lilach and Shallom, 2022).

Principles of Christian Values

Christian values are the principles that Christians believe are important in life. They are based on the teachings of Jesus Christ and the Bible. The term "Christian values" has a variety of meanings, and specific definitions can vary widely between denominations, geographical locations, and different schools of thought (Chloe, Sommerfield, Britta, 2020). However, some common Christian values include:

Love: Love is the foundation of all Christian values. It is expressed in many ways, including compassion, kindness, forgiveness, and mercy.

Justice: Justice is the belief that everyone deserves to be treated fairly, regardless of their race, gender, sexual orientation, or social status.

Peace: Peace is the absence of war and conflict. It is a goal that Christians strive for in their personal lives and in the world at large.

Hope: Hope is the belief that things will get better. It is a source of strength and resilience for Christians facing difficult times (Tascherrau-Dumouchel, Mathias, Stefan, 2022)

Forgiveness: Forgiveness is the ability to let go of anger and resentment towards someone who has wronged us. It is a way to heal ourselves and create a more peaceful world.

Honesty: Honesty is the practice of being truthful and forthright. It is a value that is essential for building trust and relationships.

Integrity: Integrity is the quality of being honest and having strong moral principles. It is a value that is essential for living a life of virtue.

Courage: Courage is the ability to face fear and danger. It is a value that is essential for standing up for what we believe in, even when it is difficult.

Perseverance: Perseverance is the ability to keep going in the face of challenges. It is a value that is essential for achieving our goals.

The Bible has long described Christian values as the Fruit of the Spirit, a list of nine attributes written by the Apostle Paul in his letter to the Galatians. These nine attributes are not exhaustive, but they are a good summary of the Christian values that are important to many Christians. These values can guide our thoughts, words, and actions, and they can help us to make better choices in our lives (Sheldon, Elliot, 2018).

“But the fruit of the Spirit is love, joy, peace, longsuffering, gentleness, goodness, faith, meekness, temperance: against such there is no law” (Galatians 5:22-23 KJV).

Theoretical Framework

Social Learning Theory

Social learning theory explains the process of acquiring social behavior through observation and imitation of others. This theory posits that learning is a cognitive activity that happens within a social setting and can transpire simply through watching or receiving direct guidance, even when motor reproduction or direct rewards are absent.

Social Learning Theory, developed by psychologists, offers a comprehensive framework for understanding how individuals learn and shape their behaviour through observation and interaction. At its core, this theory asserts that people acquire new knowledge and behaviours not only through direct experiences but also by observing and imitating the actions and attitudes of others in their social environment (Lilach and Shallom, 2022). Role models, whether they are parents, peers, teachers, or influential figures from the media, play a pivotal role in molding behaviour, as individuals are more likely to emulate the actions of those they admire. The first people children learn from in their social environments are their parents, so much knowledge and behaviours can be learned through the development of their personal values. As stated by Lilach and Shallom, 2022), this theory has found application in fields such as education, psychology, and criminology, offering insights into skill acquisition, behaviour change, and the development of personality traits through observation and interaction with others. Social learning theory is a psychological theory that states that people learn new behaviour by observing and imitating others. This theory was developed in the 1960s. The three main principles of social learning theory are:

Observational Learning: People learn new behaviour by observing others and then imitating what they see. This can happen even if the observer does not intend to learn the behaviour.

Reinforcement: People are more likely to imitate behaviour that is rewarded or reinforced.

Motivation: People are more likely to imitate behaviour that they are motivated to do. This motivation can come from internal factors, such as a desire to learn something new, or from external factors, such as a desire to be liked or accepted by others (Pearce, Uecker, Melinder, 2019).

Social learning theory is a powerful tool for understanding how people learn new behaviour. It can be used to explain a wide range of behaviour, from simple everyday activities to complex social behavior (Lilach and Shallom, 2023). Social learning theory can be applied to real-life situations:

- A child who sees their parents arguing may learn to argue themselves.
- A student who sees their teacher being rewarded for good behaviour may be more likely to behave ways similarly.
- A person who is motivated to lose weight may imitate the behaviour of someone who is already thin.

Social learning theory can be a helpful tool for parents, teachers, and other professionals who work with children and adolescents. By understanding how social learning works, they can create

environments that encourage positive behaviour and discourage negative behavior (Lilach and Shallom, 2023).

Development Theory/ Modelling Behaviour

This concept involves the initial step of observation, where individuals closely watch the behaviour or skills displayed by others in different contexts, ranging from family and school to the workplace and media (Weber, 2017). Crucially, people tend to identify with the individuals they observe, particularly if these role models possess qualities or characteristics that the observer admires. The context in which the behaviour is observed and cultural and social factors also contribute to the decision of whether to model a particular behaviour. Role models, which can be parents, teachers, peers, or public figures, are pivotal in shaping an individual's behaviours and values. Modeling behaviour is a pervasive and influential process that occurs throughout an individual's life, impacting their development, learning, and adaptation of new behaviours within various settings and social contexts (Priti, Shilpa, Shagufta, and Sapana, 2023). Understanding these principles is essential for educators, parents, and individuals seeking to guide and influence the behaviours and values of others.

Methodology

The study employs a descriptive survey design method, using a questionnaire to collect data from a sample of 200 adolescents. The study design involves the random selection of a sample of 50 Adolescents from each selected Pentecostal church in Ede and collecting data on their parental styles, personal values, and how the parental styles and religious environment influence them. The population of this study consists of 950 adolescents aged between 12 and 21 years in the selected Pentecostal Churches in Ede (namely, Redeemed Christian Church of God, Osun Province 9; Deeper Christian Life Ministries, aka Deeper Life Bible Church; Winners Chapel; And Mountain of Fire and Miracle Ministries aka MFM).

Findings

Findings reveal that each parent of the respondents exhibits parenting styles within the four styles focused on by the researchers but with significant diversity in the perceived parenting approaches within these religious communities. Each denomination exhibits distinct patterns of parenting styles among its members.

One striking observation is the prevalence of uninvolved parenting, particularly prominent within the Deeper Life Bible Church (DLBC) denomination, where most respondents perceive their parents as adopting this style. This finding raises concerns about the level of parental engagement and involvement within DLBC families. What could have been the cause? Could it be that they are occupied with too many religious activities, or could it be they believe that the children are getting enough training/teaching from the church, and so on and so forth? This highlights a potential area for further exploration and intervention.

The findings from responses to open-ended questions about the influence of the religious environment in Pentecostal churches on the development of personal values in adolescents reveal several key insights. First and foremost, the majority of respondents concur that the religious environment in Pentecostal churches holds a significant influence on their personal values, extending its impact beyond that of parental styles. Several factors contribute to this influence, encompassing doctrinal teachings, peer interactions, participation in youth programs, engagement in religious practices, the presence of role models, involvement in community service, a sense of purpose, encouragement of personal faith, and the establishment of a strong moral foundation.

The advantages of this influence are numerous, as adolescents exposed to the religious environment often develop strong moral and ethical values. They also experience spiritual growth, which can provide them with a profound sense of solace, purpose, and belonging. Furthermore, these adolescents tend to develop resilience in the face of adversity and engage in social responsibility, along with finding support and guidance from peer groups formed within the religious community.

Conclusion

Based on the findings drawn from responses to open-ended questions regarding the influence of the religious environment in Pentecostal churches on the development of personal values in adolescents, this study arrives at a conclusion that reflects the nuanced nature of this process (K. Edwards & M. Edwards. 2022). These findings have provided valuable insights into the multifaceted influence of religious environments and adolescent values, shedding light on both the advantages and drawbacks of such influences.

It is evident from the responses that the majority of adolescents in Pentecostal churches acknowledge the significant role the religious environment plays in shaping their personal values, extending its impact beyond the sphere of parental guidance (May & Robbins 2017). This influence is achieved through a combination of factors, including the church's doctrinal teachings, the peer interactions fostered within the religious community, participation in youth programs, engagement in religious practices, the guidance of role models and mentors, involvement in community service, a sense of purpose, encouragement of personal faith, and the establishment of a strong moral foundation. The advantages of this influence are manifold, as it often leads adolescents to develop strong moral and ethical values, experience spiritual growth, find solace and purpose, and build resilience in the face of adversity (Yasuma, Watanabe, Iida, Nishi, & Kawakami.2019). Moreover, it encourages social responsibility, offers a support network, and provides moral guidance, empowering adolescents with a sense of self-confidence and personal agency.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Young parents should take time to study various child upbringing and parental styles and be conscious of the ones they imbibe in nurturing their children and adolescents because they play vital roles in the development of their personal values.
2. Religious leaders and institutions in Pentecostal churches should consider promoting inclusivity and diversity within their congregations. This includes embracing individuals with varying beliefs, backgrounds, and lifestyles. Such an approach can mitigate potential drawbacks associated with religious rigidity and intolerance, as identified in the study (Juuso, 2021). Religious communities should continue to invest in youth empowerment programs that encourage adolescents to develop a strong sense of personal agency and self-confidence. These programs can play a significant role in nurturing adolescents' personal values in a positive and empowering manner (Juuso, 2021).
1. 3. Encourage interfaith and interdenominational dialogues and events to facilitate a broader understanding of diverse religious beliefs and values. This may help reduce social isolation and promote tolerance and respect among adolescents with different religious backgrounds (Bak-Coleman, Mark, Wolfram, Carl, Miquel, 2021).
2. 4. Religious institutions should recognize the importance of mental health and emotional well-being among their members, including adolescents. They can provide resources and support for individuals who may be dealing with mental health challenges and ensure that their congregations are places where individuals feel safe seeking help and guidance (Juuso, 2021).

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